

Green House

Developed by: Limitless Harmony, Creators: Alix Dvorak & Adam Lupu

Article contributed by: Elizabeth Johnston

Keywords

Climate-change Education, Collaborative Problem-solving, Economics, Risk Management, Strategic Decision-making, Sustainability

Introduction

Green House is a card game designed for players 12 and older to save the planet from the effects of the climate crisis. Developed by Alix Dvorak and Adam Lupu, this card game provides players with 64 “Solution-Focused Action Cards” focused on how families, businesses, nonprofits, and government entities can address the climate crisis. In team play, players collaborate and consider how to act on events (Limitless Harmony, 2021). Backed by a 2020 Kickstarter project, Limitless Harmony first published the deck for backers and is now available on the Green House website. Players grapple with obstacles such as pollution, time, cost, and hopelessness as they take actions to “clean the sky” (Limitless Harmony, 2021). Green House provides a low floor for entry into the game, as players do not need to be an expert on the climate crisis to play. The creators describe several reasons to focus on the climate crisis within a gaming context, such as providing an opportunity to discuss these big ideas with friends and family and making it easier to access and understand possible solutions (Limitless Harmony, 2020).

Facts

Release date:	2020
Developer:	Limitless Harmony, Creators: Alix Dvorak & Adam Lupu
Game type:	Analog
Number of players:	Team Play Mode, 1–8 players; Role Play Mode, 3–8 players
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	20–30 minutes
Languages:	English
Environment:	Tabletop space for game pieces and space for all players
Material:	The game website includes an overview of the game and a how-to-play video (https://www.greenhousegame.com). It also provides access to all climate solutions with links to additional resources (https://www.greenhousegame.com/solutions).

Price: Card game: \$33; Print & Play (PDF of game): \$10; school set (5 copies of the game & Classroom and Conversation Guide): \$160.

Resonance & Criticism

There is little information from players and experts about their thoughts on this game. BoardGameGeek (n.d.) lists a rating of 7.2/10 with three reviews. A video review by one user highlights key aspects of the gameplay; however, Tolson (2021) offers positive remarks about how the events are easy to relate to because of their connection to real-world events such as wildfires or hurricanes. Other player viewpoints are outlined on the Green House website, which provides positive reviews of the gameplay and the connection to the climate crisis (Limitless Harmony, 2021). According to Douglas & Brauer (2021), gamification can be an effective tool for supporting players' understanding of sustainability, though they do not specifically review Green House.

Game Principle & Process

Figure 1. Example event and action cards from Green House, illustrating climate-related challenges and solution-focused actions within the game system (Limitless Harmony; Alix Dvorak & Adam Lupu). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Green House focuses on how greenhouse gas emissions contribute to the climate crisis and ways to reverse their effects, such as reducing the burning of fossil fuels and shifting agricultural practices (Bruhwiler et al., 2021; Mikhaylov & Moiseev, 2020; Omotoso & Omotayo, 2023).

The creators suggest starting with “Team Play Mode” (Limitless Harmony, 2021), designed for 1 to 8 players, with modifications for single- and two-player games. Players work collaboratively to eliminate “Greenhouse Gas” (GHG). Actions taken impact all players and their efforts to convert GHG (angry clouds) into “Clear Sky” (happy clouds). Players lose the game if they collectively run out of money, time, hope, or clean air.

Players’ hands include four “Action Cards” (AC), which represent ways to impact the climate crisis. A turn begins with a player selecting an “Event Card” (EC) from the deck (see Figure 1). ECs are environmental consequences that might occur, such as “Fish Extinction!” or “Climate Refugees.” After selecting a card, the player must adjust the GHG, “Money,” and “Hope” tokens to account for the effects. For instance, if the player selects the “Global Drought!” card, then they would flip 3 “Clear Sky” tokens to the GHG side, take away 3 “Money” tokens, and flip one of the heart “Hope” tokens to the broken side. Next, the player selects an AC to play. These cards have the potential to impact the effects of an EC. For example, if a player selected “Befriend Your Representatives,” then they would earn 2 “Money” tokens and would flip one broken heart to the “Hope” side. Not all ACs have positive effects. Cards like “Make Smarter Grids” take away GHG tokens but also cost money. Players can make more impact by going on “Momentum Runs.” ACs with a momentum icon allow for up to 2 players to add an AC. At the end of a turn, players draw new ACs to fill their hands back to 4 cards.

The “Role Play Mode,” for 3 to 8 players, modifies play. Players manage their own money. They can only play an AC if they have the funds and are out of the game if they run out of money. Actions do not take immediate effect, as another player needs to back a proposed action with the appropriate funding. Also, players select one of four roles: family, business, nonprofit, or government. Each has “special powers” that change the game. For instance, if a player has the government role, they collect two “Money” tokens from each player at the start of their turn.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Green House focuses on helping players understand the climate crisis. ACs allow players to learn about ways that nonprofits, businesses, families, and government entities can change their impact on the planet. Each AC includes a QR code that links to a resource with more details. For instance, the “Reduce Food Waste” card links to an article from the BBC that highlights the environmental impact of food waste. These links provide a starting point for players to learn more about the issues the game addresses. The ECs describe how the climate crisis is impacting the planet. For example, the “Extreme Storms” card says, “Rainstorms, tornadoes, and snowstorms are more frequent and last longer, causing chaos and costly

damage.” These cards do not include links to additional information, so it is up to the player to investigate the topic further.

The gameplay is straightforward, allowing both players and the teacher to focus on the game’s climate-crisis content. Discussions about the economics of the climate crisis and people’s feelings of climate anxiety could be supported. Players could discuss the implications of events or actions in terms of the money it costs or the potential for hopelessness. When purchasing the school set, educators also receive “Classroom and Conversation Guides.” Facilitation is an important component of using serious games in the classroom as students grapple with complex ideas. Van Schaik (2023) writes, “The way in which the educator talks to their students and engages them in conversation is of relevance, as this might affect how the climate change-related uncertainties in the games are interpreted in the educational setting” (p. 1901–1902).

Effectiveness

Although there is no research on the effectiveness of the Green House game, researchers are investigating the use of gamification to address the environmental crisis (Douglas & Brauer, 2021; Flood et al., 2018; van Schaik, 2023). According to Douglas & Brauer (2021), “Gamification, the application of game design principles to a nongaming context, has been used to promote pro-environmental behaviors” (p. 89). Flood et al. (2018) outline several potential benefits of high-quality serious games focused on adaptation to climate change, such as challenging players’ beliefs and influencing how they apply their understandings to the real world. In comparison, van Schaik (2023) highlights the potential for games to help players cope with the uncertainties of the climate crisis.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

The climate crisis evolves as the planet changes due to human activity, scientists’ knowledge deepens, and new understandings of potential solutions emerge. The AC and EC capture the climate crisis at the time of publication (2020). The AC cards include QR codes to resources that might not be accessible in the future, or the science might no longer support these actions.

The climate crisis is not equitably felt across humanity. The conversations that emerge as players engage with the ideas might be challenging depending on their experiences. For example, “Students might experience psychological distress, presumably especially if they have previously been impacted by climate catastrophes or other adverse and uncertain circumstances” (van Schaik, 2023, p. 1901).

The game suggests an age of 12+, but the developers’ content suggests that younger children might be able to play. They note that the math required is simple and that the game’s pictures will engage younger children (Limitless Harmony, 2021). There is nothing specific in the rules or suggestions on how to modify gameplay for younger users.

Reviewer(s): Anna Sorgatz

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